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Inhibitory effect of formoterol on coronaviruses

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ABSTRACT

Formoterol is a long-acting β_2 agonist (LABA) used as a bronchodilator in the management of asthma and COPD.

The results of two studies suggest that inhaled formoterol might be used as additional therapeutic agent in the treatment of COVID-19, especially in patients with asthma or COPD, but further research is necessary.

FORMOTEROL

Formoterol, also known as eformoterol, is a long-acting β_2 agonist (LABA) used as a bronchodilator in the management of asthma and COPD.

Formoterol has an extended duration of action (up to 12 hours) compared to short-acting β_2 agonist such as salbutamol (albuterol), which are effective for 4-6 hours. It is used as oral inhalation^{1,2}.

INHIBITORY EFFECT ON CORONAVIRUSES

Findings of a study conducted by Yamaya and coworkers (2020) suggest that glycopyrronium, **formoterol**, and a combination of glycopyrronium, formoterol, and budesonide inhibit HCoV-229E (human coronavirus 229E) replication partly by inhibiting receptor expression and/or endosomal function and that these drugs modulate infection-induced inflammation in the airway³.

In the docking studies (Arya, et al), sixteen FDA approved drugs, including chloroquine and **formoterol**, was found to bind the target enzyme (the papain-like protease of SARS-CoV-2 that is essential for viral life-cycle) with significant affinity and good geometry, suggesting their potential to be utilized against the virus⁴.

CONCLUSION

The results of these two studies suggest that inhaled formoterol might be used as additional therapeutic agent in the treatment of COVID-19, especially in patients with asthma or COPD, but further research is necessary.

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